

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS HANDMADE BATH SOAPS IN RAMANATHAPURAM DISTRICT

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Received: Jan 25, 2026

Accepted: Feb 18, 2026

Published: Feb 19, 2026

Abstract

This empirical study examines the factors influencing customer preference towards handmade bath soaps in the context of increasing demand for natural, herbal and eco-friendly personal care products. Handmade bath soaps, made using natural and Ayurvedic ingredients, are perceived as safer and more beneficial for skin health. Despite growing awareness, Commercial bath soaps continue to dominate the market due to strong branding, affordability and wide availability. The study aims to analyze the influence of socio-economic characteristics, consumer awareness, purchase behaviour and attitude on the preference for handmade bath soaps. The findings reveal that factors such as Skin benefits, natural ingredients, quality and price significantly influence customer preference towards handmade bath soaps, providing valuable insights in improving product acceptance and market reach.

Keywords

Handmade Bath Soaps, Consumer Preference, Nature and Herbal Products, Purchase Behaviour and Skin Health.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, consumers have shown a growing preference for natural, herbal and eco-friendly personal care products, leading to increased demand for handmade bath soaps. Rising Awareness about the harmful effects of chemicals such as parabens, sulphates and synthetic fragrances has encouraged customers to shift towards safer and skin-friendly alternatives. Handmade bath soaps are generally prepared using natural and Ayurvedic ingredients, making them safer and more beneficial for skin health. These soaps are often produced in small batches, ensuring better quality control and uniqueness in formulation.

Factors such as quality, fragrance, skin benefits, price, packaging and ingredient transparency play a vital role in influencing customer preference. Additionally, socio-economic characteristics like age, income and residential status significantly impact buying behaviour and product choice. Therefore, understanding both product attributes and demographic factors is essential for marketers to effectively position handmade bath soaps in the competitive personal care market.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite the increasing awareness and acceptance of handmade bath soaps, Commercial bath soaps continue to dominate the market due to strong branding, affordability and wide availability. This situation highlights the need to examine consumer awareness, purchase behaviour and attitudes towards handmade bath soaps. Hence, the present study titled “An Empirical Study of Factors Influencing Customer Preference towards Handmade Bath Soaps” seeks to analyze the factors influencing consumer preference and the level of agreement towards handmade bath soaps.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- ❖ To study the socio-economic profile of consumers and its influence on their preference towards handmade bath soaps.
- ❖ To identify the key factors influencing customer preference for handmade bath soaps such as price, skin benefits and natural ingredients.
- ❖ To analyze consumer awareness, purchase behaviour and level of agreement towards handmade bath soaps.

1.3 Scope of the Study

- The study covers consumer preference related to handmade bath soaps based on price, place of purchase and awareness.
- It includes analysis of factors influencing purchase decisions and attitude towards handmade bath soaps.
- The study is confined to selected respondents and geographical area and focuses only on handmade bath soap products.

1.4 Literature Review

Anumalini.M (2025) – The paper titled “A Study on Consumer Brand Preference of Skincare Soaps, Puthanampatti, Thiruchirapalli District”. Findings show that factors like place, product, price, promotion and psychological aspects influence purchasing behaviour with Lux and Lifebuoy preferred. The research highlights how consumer attributes and marketing affect brand choice in the FMCG skincare soap market.

Karthikeyan.M (2022) – The paper titled “A Study on Consumer Brand Preferences of Skincare Product Soap in Chennai Region” this study shows that quality, brand image and advertising strongly influence brand choice. Findings highlight preferred brands and reasons for switching. The study suggests marketer’s tailor strategies to consumer needs to improve preference and satisfaction.

1.5 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study considers only selected factors influencing customer preference and excludes other possible factors such as promotional strategies and seasonal demand.

II – MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

2.1 Emergence of Handmade Bath Soap

i) Growing Awareness of Skin Health:

Consumers have become more conscious about maintaining healthy skin and avoiding skin-related problems. Some soaps contain synthetic chemicals that may cause dryness, irritation or allergies. This has led consumers to look for safer alternatives that are gentle on the skin. Handmade bath soaps are perceived to be mild and nourishing due to their natural formulation.

ii) Preference for Natural and Herbal Ingredients:

Consumers today prefer products made from natural and herbal ingredients rather than artificial chemicals. Handmade bath soaps often use plant-based oils, herbs and essential oils that are considered safe and beneficial. The presence of Ayurvedic and Organic ingredients further enhances consumer trust. Such ingredients are believed to improve skin quality and provide long term-benefits.

iii) Environmental and Eco-friendly Concerns:

Environmental sustainability has become an important factor influencing consumer buying behaviour. Handmade bath soaps are generally produced using eco-friendly methods and biodegradable ingredients. Many brands use minimal or recyclable packaging to reduce environmental impact. Consumers who are environmentally conscious prefer products that cause less harm to nature.

iv) Influence of Social Media and Word of Mouth:

Social media platforms play a major role in spreading awareness about handmade bath soaps. Consumers often rely on reviews, recommendations and testimonials shared online. Word of mouth from friends and family also creates trust and credibility. Influencers and small business promotions have helped handmade soap brands reach wider audiences. These factors have positively influenced consumer interest and purchase decisions.

v) Support for Local and Small-Scale Industries:

Many consumers prefer to support local artisans and small-scale industries through their purchasing choices. Handmade bath soaps are often produced by cottage industries and small entrepreneurs. Buying handmade soaps helps generate employment and traditional skills. This support has encouraged the growth and emergence of handmade bath soaps.

2.2 Period of the Study

The Study covers a period of six months from SEPTEMBER 2025 to FEBRAURY 2026. The data has been collected from the handmade bath soaps in Ramanathapuram District.

2.3 Methodology

Methodology is an aspect of any research investigation. It enables the investigation to look at the problems in a systematic, meaningful and orderly way. The goal of the study is to measure how 50 sample respondents in Ramanathapuram district factors influence the customer preference towards handmade bath soaps. The study is based on both primary and secondary data.

2.4 Framework of Analysis

After collection of data it is analyzed with suitable statistical tools. The data were classified into tables for the purpose analysis and interpretation. The tools used is Correlation.

2.5 Correlation Analysis

The Correlation Analysis refers to the techniques used in measuring the closeness of the relationship between the variables.

“Correlation is a measure of degree of relatedness of variables” - **Ken Black**

2.6 Application of Co-Efficient Of Correlation

TABLE 2.6.1

Correlations			In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Prefer Handmade]	In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Buy as gift]
In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Prefer Handmade]	Pearson Correlation		1	.249
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.081
	N		50	50
In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Buy as gift]	Pearson Correlation		.249	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.081	
	N		50	50

Source: Primary Data

Here, $r = 0.249$, $p = 0.081$

Interpretation

The results from the table 2.6.1 shows that the co-efficient of correlation ($r = 0.249$, $p > 0.05$). It is concluded that there is no statistically significant relationship between Prefer Handmade and Buy as Gift on Handmade Bath soaps.

2.6.2 Application of Co-Efficient Of Correlation

TABLE 2.6.2

Correlations			In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Willingness to pay more]	In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Natural Ingredients]
In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Willingness to pay more]	Pearson Correlation		1	.460**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.001
	N		50	50
In what way do you agree when buying Handmade Bath soaps: [Natural Ingredients]	Pearson Correlation		.460**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	
	N		50	50

Source: Primary Data

Here, $r = 0.460$, $p = 0.001$

Interpretation

The results from the table 2.6.2 shows that the co-efficient of correlation ($r = 0.460$, $p < 0.05$). It is concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between Willingness to pay more and Natural Ingredients on Handmade Bath soaps.

III – FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Findings

- It shows that the co-efficient of correlation ($r= 0.249$, $p > 0.05$). It is concluded that there is no statistically significant relationship between Prefer Handmade and Buy as Gift on Handmade Bath soaps.
- It shows that the co-efficient of correlation ($r= 0.460$, $p < 0.05$). It is concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between Willingness to pay more and Natural Ingredients on Handmade Bath soaps.

3.2 Suggestions

- Special gift boxes. Festive wrapping and premium packaging may encourage customers to buy handmade soap for gifting purposes.
- Offer combo packs and limited-edition gift sets during festivals to stimulate gift purchases.
- Advertisement and social media promotions should highlight handmade soaps as thoughtful, eco-friendly and premium gifting options.
- Future studies can explore other factors like income, occasion, packaging appeal and brand image influencing gift purchases.

3.3 Conclusion

The study concludes that customer preference for handmade bath soaps is influenced by factors such as natural ingredients, skin benefits, eco-friendliness and product transparency. While some consumers may prefer handmade bath soaps for personal use, they do not necessarily associate them with gifting purposes. While appropriate strategies, improved visibility and attractive packaging, so it can compete effectively and expand their market share in the future.

Reference

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